

Effects of Faraday Rotation on Microwave Remote Sensing from Space at L-Band

D.M. Le Vine and M. Kao

Laboratory for Hydrospheric Processes/Code 975

NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center

Greenbelt, Maryland 20771

Phone: 301-286-8059; FAX: 301-286-0294; Email: dmlevine@meneg.gsfc.nasa.gov

Abstract -- The effect of Faraday rotation on the remote sensing of soil moisture from space is investigated using the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) to obtain electron density profiles and the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF) to model the magnetic field. With a judicious choice of satellite orbit (6 am, sunsynchronous) the errors caused by ignoring Faraday rotation are less than 1 K at incidence angles less than 40 degrees.

INTRODUCTION

An L-band radiometer in space could provide global maps of surface soil moisture and contribute to the measurement of other important parameters of the earth surface [1]. Furthermore, advances in technology such as the development of aperture synthesis [2] and inflatable structures [3] have enhanced the prospect that a practical sensor can be deployed in space in the near future. Among the concerns associated with operating at this low frequency is rotation of the polarization vector due to the ionosphere (Faraday rotation). Faraday rotation can result in errors for conical scanners and cross-track imagers which view the surface at non-nadir incidence angles (i.e. where the emissivity at vertical and horizontal polarization differ).

At frequencies near L-band (1.4 GHz) the change in direction of the polarization vector of a linearly polarized wave propagating through the ionosphere can be written [4]:

$$\Delta\phi = (\pi/cv^2) \int v_p^2 v_B \cos(\theta_B) ds \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\phi$ is the change in direction (radians), ds is distance along the ray path, v = frequency (Hz), v_p = electron plasma frequency (Hz) $\approx 9\sqrt{N_e}$ where N_e is the electron density in $\#/m^3$, v_B = electron "cyclotron" frequency (Hz) = $qB/(2\pi M_e)$, and θ_B is the angle between the magnetic field, B , and the direction of propagation, θ . The effect of $\Delta\phi$ on a linearly polarized radiometer is to mix horizontally and vertically polarized emissions received from the surface. For example, in the case of a

horizontally polarized receiver, the apparent brightness temperature, T_B , is:

$$T_B = [\epsilon_h \cos^2(\Delta\phi) + \epsilon_v \sin^2(\Delta\phi)] T_o \quad (2)$$

and the error incurred by ignoring Faraday rotation is:

$$\Delta T_B = T_o [\epsilon_h - \epsilon_v] \sin^2(\Delta\phi) \quad (3)$$

where T_o is the physical temperature of the surface and ϵ_h and ϵ_v are the emissivities of the surface for horizontal and vertical polarization, respectively.

EXAMPLES OF FARADAY ROTATION

Faraday rotation, $\Delta\phi$, has been computed using the International Reference Ionosphere [5] to generate electron density profiles and the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF) to model the earth's magnetic field. Figure 1 shows Faraday rotation as a function of local time for a hypothetical sensor at an altitude of 675 km and at 35° N. latitude and 75° W. longitude. Curves are shown for summer and winter of 1995 (solar minimum) and 1990 (solar maximum). Notice that $\Delta\phi$ is minimum near 6 am and that the evening (6 pm) is somewhat worse than the morning. A sun-synchronous orbit is advantageous for the measurement of soil moisture (to avoid diurnal effects), and the 6 am crossing clearly is a good choice as far as Faraday rotation is concerned. Figure 2 shows Faraday rotation as a function of longitude for latitude of 20 and 60 degrees. These examples are for 6 am, 675 km altitude and for the summer of 1990 and 1995. Summer 1990 (solar maximum) is a worse case. The $\Delta\phi$ for 1995 (solar minimum) is much less. The angles, $\Delta\phi$, shown in this case (1995) are also representative of the values of Faraday rotation obtained in winter for both 1990 and 1995 at latitudes between 20-60 degrees. Faraday rotation also depends on orbit altitude and this is illustrated in Figure 3 for local time of 6 am. Note that the $\Delta\phi$ in Figures 1-3 are for a nadir directed ray path ($\theta = 0$). The results can be corrected approximately for incidence angle, θ , using: $\Delta\phi(\theta) \approx \Delta\phi(0)/\cos(\theta)$.

EFFECT ON BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURE

The effect of Faraday rotation on observed brightness temperature, depends on the emissivities, $\epsilon_{h,v}$, of the surface as shown in (2) and (3). Assuming a flat, homogenous half-space and neglecting effects such as roughness and vegetation cover:

$$\epsilon_{h,v}(\theta) = 1 - |R_{h,v}(\theta)|^2 \quad (4)$$

where $R_{h,v}(\theta)$ is the Fresnel reflection coefficient of the surface. For the ideal (i.e. flat) surface the Fresnel reflection coefficients are functions of the incidence angle, θ , and the relative dielectric constant of the soil, e_r , in the form:

$$R_v(\theta) = \frac{e_r \cos(\theta) - \sqrt{e_r - \sin^2(\theta)}}{e_r \cos(\theta) + \sqrt{e_r - \sin^2(\theta)}} \quad (5)$$

$$R_h(\theta) = \frac{\cos(\theta) - \sqrt{e_r - \sin^2(\theta)}}{\cos(\theta) + \sqrt{e_r - \sin^2(\theta)}}$$

In the calculations done here, the relative dielectric constant, e_r , has been expressed as a function of volumetric moisture, W , in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{\text{real}} &= 3.1 + 17.36W + 63.12W^2 \\ e_{\text{imag}} &= 0.031 + 4.65W + 20.42W^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

which were obtained from Wang [6; Eqns 7-8] assuming a frequency of 1.4 GHz, a soil porosity of 0.5, a relative dielectric constant of rocks of 5, and letting the parameter $\beta = 6.5$ and $f_m = 5$. This is a reasonable representation for clay soils.

Figure 4 shows the error in brightness temperature incurred by ignoring Faraday rotation for a moderately wet soil ($W = 0.4$) as a function of incidence angle. Figure 5 shows how this error depends on soil wetness. Notice that the error is somewhat larger for wet soil. This occurs even though brightness temperature decreases with increased water content because the error depends on the difference between the emissivity at horizontal and vertical polarization. Figures 4-5 have been plotted as a function of $\Delta\phi$ along a nadir path to facilitate comparison with Figures 1-3, but $\Delta\phi$ along the appropriate (i.e. slant) path was used to calculate ΔT_B .

CONCLUSION

Assuming a sensor in a sunsynchronous orbit with a 6 am crossing time, Figures 1-3 indicate Faraday rotation on the order of 6 degrees or less is to be expected at nadir (except possibly near the poles). Figure 4-5 indicate that not correcting for this change in polarization will result in errors of less than 1 K in observations over a flat soil surface, even at incidence angles as large as 40 degrees. Such an error is comparable to requirements for accuracy of sensors to monitor soil moisture [1].

REFERENCES

- [1]. Le Vine, D.M., T.T. Wilheit, R.E. Murphy and C.T. Swift, "A Multifrequency Microwave Radiometer of the Future", IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing, Vol; 27 (#2), pp 193-199, 1989.
- [2]. Le Vine, D.M., A.J. Griffis, C.T. Swift and T.J. Jackson, "ESTAR: A Synthetic Aperture Microwave Radiometer for Remote Sensing Applications", Proc. IEEE, Vol 82 (#12), pp 1787-1801, Dec., 1994.
- [3]. Njoku, E, J. Sercel, W. Wilson and Y. Rahmat-Samii, "Soil Moisture Path-Finder, A Low Cost Passive Spaceborne System Using Inflatable Structures", Presented at Meeting on Microwave Radiometry & Remote Sensing, Boston, MA, November, 1996.
- [4]. Thompson, A.R., J.M. Moran, G.W. Swenson, Interferometry and Synthesis in Radio Astronomy, J. Wiley & Sons, pp 442-445, 1986.

Fig.1: Faraday rotation (degrees) as a function of local time. Location: 35° N. Latitude & 75° W. Longitude; Altitude = 675 km; 1990 is a solar maximum and 1995 is a solar minimum. Su = summer and wi = winter.

- [5]. Bilitza, D., K. Rawer, L. Bossy and T. Gulyaeva, "International Reference Ionosphere -- Past, Present and Future", Adv. Space Res., Vol 13 (#3), pp 3-23, 1993.
- [6]. Wang, J.R., "The Dielectric Properties of Soil Water Mixtures at Microwave Frequencies", Radio Sci, Vol 15, pp 970-985, 1980.

Fig.2: Faraday rotation (degrees) as a function of longitude. Latitude = 20 and 60 degrees; Local time = 6 am; Altitude = 675 km. 1990 = solar maximum and 1995 = solar minimum. The curves are for summer.

Fig.4: Error caused by Faraday rotation for several different incidence angles. The abscissa is Faraday rotation angle along the nadir path. $W = 0.4$; Surface Temperature = 293 K; Horizontal polarization.

Fig.3: Faraday rotation (at nadir) as a function of altitude. Location: 35° N. Latitude & 75° W. Longitude; Local time = 6 am; 1990 is a solar maximum and 1995 is a solar minimum. Su = summer and wi = winter.

Fig.5: Dependence of brightness temperature error caused by ignoring Faraday rotation on soil water content. The abscissa is the Faraday rotation at nadir. Examples are for volumetric water content $W = 0.1$ and 0.6 and for an incidence angle of 40 degrees. Horizontal polarization.